

Some Metallurgical observations in Rare Earth added Magnesium Alloys-A Review

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ABSTRACT-Magnesium alloys with rare earth additions are being used and researched upon extensively. This paper reviews latest work on Magnesium alloys with Yttrium,Gadolinium and Terbium rare earth metals.Property improvements and corrosion resistance are discussed and mechanisms of alloy formation are explained.

1.0.INTRODUCTION

Magnesium as a metal has an atomic number 24.305 and melting point of 650 Celcius.It is abundantly available in the earth's crust, but it is always available in the combined form only ,mostly in the form of the ore dolomite. It is the 8th most abundant element in the Universe ,according to the U.S Geological survey. It is the lightest of all structural metals, while not sacrificing its strength. This property becomes important in its applications which require portability, such as luggage, laptop computers and cell phones.China is the leading producer of Magnesium and th estimated global production of Magnesium is 1.4 million tonnes in 2025.The Magnesium alloy market is expected to grow in the future.

2.0 MAGNESIUM ALLOYS

Magnesium and its alloys are lighter than Aluminium,Titanium and Stainless Steel.[1]Global Magnesium market is expected to grow at more than 9% in the 2020s.[2]Magnesium is very reactive with the atmosphere. In spite of this property, corrosion rates compared to mild steel are better. There are 2 types of Magnesium alloys-Wrought and cast alloys. Wrought alloys are not used because they have poor formability. The reason for poor formability is the textured structure of the alloy, This textured structure can be removed by adding rare earth additions like Yttrium(Y),Gadolinium(Gd),Niodymium(Nd),Cerium(Ce) and Lanthanum. Moreover, the change in texture occurs for very small percentage additions(<0.01%) of rare earths.[3]

3.0.RARE EARTH ADDITIONS

Rare Earth element alloy addition in Magnesium was initially used as Misch metal, which consisted of Cerium, Lanthanum, Neodymium and Pr.This alloy consists of 50% Cerium and 25% Lanthanum. The addition of Yttrium has been shown to have maximum effect on strengthening of rare earth magnesium alloys and hence a large amount of commercial Yttrium based Magnesium alloys have been developed.[2]A study on the effect of rare earth metals on Magnesium alloys has been conducted using first principles. This study has established that δf electrons and atomic radii play an important role in the strengthening process.[4]The elastic moduli and shear moduli have been calculated and analysed in this study.

Yttrium and Gadolinium contribute to age hardening and good high temperature strength in Magnesium alloys. This fact is due to the precipitation of β phase with DO19 crystal structure. These precipitates increase on increasing Gadolinium % age, giving rise to increase in hardness. Increase in % age of Yttrium decreases hardness and increases % elongation. So, these two facts put together offer an opportunity to the researcher to try out various tailor made compositions, which will give an optimum combination of strength and hardness.[5]

3.1.Precipitation hardening in Mg alloys

Mg-Gd Alloys Mg-3Gd-0.4Ce alloy was developed using Disintegrated Deposition Method (DMD) followed by hot extrusion. The developed alloy exhibited superior mechanical properties i.e. strength and ductility.[15]

Ga is a typical representative of the heavy RE elements, with the atomic weight of 157.25, the density of 7.89g/cm³ and the melting point of 1312 °C. It produces various intermetallic compounds with

Mg such as Mg₅Cd, Mg₃Cd, Mg₂Cd and MgCd which may mostly be brittle in nature.[8] Gd atoms were found to segregate along dislocations forming Cottrell atmospheres. For slowly diffusing atoms, these Cottrell atmospheres slow down dislocation movement by forming a drag force.[13] This slowing down gives rise to strengthening.

Figure 1 shows Cottrell atmosphere

Cottrell atmospheres are interstitial sites near which a small atom can sit. This leads to hardening and strengthening.

Effect of Gd concentration on Mg has been studied. Gd was varied in the range 0.32 at % to 2.57 atomic %. Hardness and yield strength variation were studied and it was found that hardness

varied linearly with atomic % Gd. The maximum values of elongation were observed for Mg10Gd and Mg2GdZr alloys, respectively. After the taking into account, grain size strengthening, the yield strength of Mg-Gd alloys was found to increase linearly with c^n , where c is the Gd concentration and $n=1/2$ or $2/3$. [6] A maximum strength of 400 MPa has been found in Mg-225 Gd by Drits. [10]

3.2 Growth kinetics in Mg alloys

One of the first studies on precipitation reactions occurring in Magnesium-Gadolinium alloys was by P.J.Apps et al. They have noted differences in precipitate morphology and volume fraction with change in Gadolinium content. [8] Electron microscopic studies have been conducted on the supersaturated solution Mg-225 Gd by Rokhlin et al. [12] When grain size is at the nanolevel reverse Hall Petch equation holds good. [16] Figure 2 below shows design of Magnesium alloy with Rare Earth addition.

Figure 2 shows Magnesium alloy design with rare earth addition

3.3. Hot tearing susceptibility of Mg-Gd alloys

Addition of Gd affects the hot tearing susceptibility. At 2% Gd, it was found to be a maximum due to the presence of columnar grains and a low volume of eutectic liquid. At 10 % Gd, it was found to be maximum. The grain structure in this case was found to be equiaxed and also the

amount of eutectic liquid was found to be more. This was thought to be the reason for this phenomenon.[13]

Figure 3 shows crack and shearing mechanism in Mg alloys

3.4 Corrosion behavior

Gadolinium coating has been given on Magnesium alloys and corrosion behavior has been studied with the help of potentiodynamic polarization curves and electrochemical impedance spectroscopy. The coating on analysis using EDS showed the presence of Magnesium and Gadolinium oxides, which may have formed a protective layer to prevent corrosion.[11]

Medical applications

Magnesium and its alloys have been researched due to its biocompatibility with the human body.

Two novel rare earth-based Mg alloys, R1 (MgYZrRE) and R2 (MgZnYZrRE) have been used in medical applications. Collagen and HF coatings have been developed on these rare earth alloys in order to use the alloys with improved strength and corrosion resistance for the purpose of scaffolding in cardiovascular stents.[7] Each alloy displayed a different corrosion behavior. MgZn was least susceptible to corrosion followed by MgZnCaGd and MgZnCa

4.0. CONCLUSIONS

Magnesium and its alloys are being seen as substitutes for Aluminium alloys. Rare earth additions make Magnesium alloys more attractive in their properties. The future will see more and more rare earth containing Magnesium alloys being used in Industrial applications. Mechanisms of growth, precipitation, hot tearing and corrosion behaviour in Mg based alloys with rare earth additions have been reviewed.

5.0. REFERENCES

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